

ULTRASONIC FATIGUE OF CARBON FIBER FABRIC REINFORCED POLYPHENYLENE SULFIDE IN THE VERY HIGH CYCLE FATIGUE REGIME: TEST PROCEDURE AND MICROSTRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Continuously fiber reinforced polymers and particularly carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) are increasingly used in structural parts over the last years. Especially in aircrafts these structural parts are loaded with more than 10^8 cycles during their lifetime. To gain a comprehensive knowledge about the fatigue behavior and the corresponding failure mechanisms of CFRP in the Very High Cycle Fatigue (VHCF) regime in economically reasonable times a new ultrasonic testing facility for cyclic three point bending has been developed at the Institute of Materials Science and Engineering (WKK) at the University of Kaiserslautern, Germany. The ultrasonic testing facility works with a frequency of 20 kHz and allows VHCF-experiments with polymer composites up to 10^9 cycles in only 12 days. To ensure a specimen temperature far below the glass transition temperature of the polymer the cyclic loading is split in pulse-pause sequences. The investigated material is a commercially available carbon fiber fabric reinforced polyphenylene sulfide (CF-PPS). 3D-scanning laser vibrometry was used to determine the strain distribution and the oscillation mode at 20 kHz as well as to calibrate the cyclic loading amplitudes. Constant amplitude tests were performed with a load ratio between $0.29 < R_r < 0.51$ and were continuously monitored by single spot laser vibrometry and IR thermography. An exponential decrease of the bearable cyclic shear stress amplitude from 10^7 up to 2×10^9 cycles could be observed. The VHCF experiments have been interrupted in defined fatigue states for microscopic investigations. Additionally the evolution of the surface crack density has been determined for different load levels as function of the number of cycles. Based on complementary SEM investigations the VHCF failure mechanisms of CF-PPS were studied.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) are the state of the art materials for highly loaded lightweight structures and are getting more and more important especially in the aircraft and automotive industry. During their time in service of more than 20 years structural CFRP parts are often loaded with up to 10^{11} cycles [1]. This range of more than 10^8 cycles is known as Very High Cycle Fatigue (VHCF) regime [2]. To utilize the full mechanical performance of CFRP for lightweight applications, the fatigue behavior has to be well understood. However primarily the VHCF behavior of CFRP is insufficiently characterized so far caused by very long running times of VHCF experiments. Only a few investigations up to 3×10^8 cycles have been realized with testing frequencies between 3 and 100 Hz [3-6]. Using testing frequencies of about 100 Hz one VHCF experiment up to 10^9 cycles would take at least 115 days. To realize the required VHCF experiments up to 10^9 cycles in an economic reasonable time, a new ultrasonic testing facility, so called "UltraFAST-WKK-Kaiserslautern", working with cyclic 3-point bending, has been developed at WKK.

2 ULTRASONIC TEST FACILITY FOR CYCLIC 3-POINT-BENDING

The VHCF experiments of CF-PPS have been carried out with an ultrasonic testing facility for cyclic 3-point bending at ambient temperature ($T = 23^{\circ}\text{C}$). The ultimate number of cycles was defined to $N = 10^9$. To avoid unacceptable heating of the CFRP specimens during the ultrasonic pulses with a frequency of 20 kHz, the experiments are split in pulse-pause sequences. Additionally the specimens have been permanently cooled with dry compressed air. A maximum increase of specimen surface temperature of only 4°C during the ultrasonic pulses of 100 ms was measured for the undamaged specimens and therefore well below the glass transition temperature of CF-PPS with $T_g \approx 90^{\circ}\text{C}$ [7]. Another essential condition to avoid unacceptable heating is the permanent contact between the loading device and the CFRP specimen. To realize this permanent contact, all experiments have been performed with load ratios between $0.29 < R_{\tau} < 0.51$. The ultrasonic testing facility described above is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: New developed ultrasonic testing facility for cyclic 3-point bending of CFRP, called “UltraFAST-WKK-Kaiserslautern”

The fatigue load is generated by a digital high power ultrasonic generator ① which transforms the system voltage of 50 Hz into a high frequency alternating electric voltage of 20 kHz. This voltage is relayed to the ultrasonic resonance system ② which consists of a converter, a booster and a loading device ③. The first part, the converter, transforms the high frequency electric voltage into a mechanical oscillation of the same frequency via the inverse piezoelectric effect [8]. The booster as the second part stabilizes and amplifies the generated oscillation due to its geometry. The amplified mechanical oscillation, which lies in the range of up to $60 \mu\text{m}$, is transmitted to the CFRP specimen supported by a variable shoulder unit ④. The principle of high-frequency mechanical oscillation at ultrasonic frequencies for metal fatigue testing in the VHCF regime is already well known [9-12]. Compared to literature and in contrast to conventional ultrasonic fatigue testing devices for metals, the CFRP specimen at this facility is not a fixed part of the ultrasonic resonance system. Accordingly a specific VHCF specimen design is required to achieve the first bending eigenmode of the CFRP specimen precisely at the resonance frequency of the entire resonance system. Further details to the VHCF testing facility including thermographic investigations are given in Backe et al. [15].

2.1 3D-Scanning Laser Vibrometry

After FEM simulations of the specimen geometry high resolution non-contact measurements using a 3D-Scanning-Laser vibrometer (3D-SLV) were performed to determine the oscillation behavior as well as the strain distribution of the CF-PPS specimens in the initial state and after VHCF loading. The measurements, realized in cooperation with Polytec GmbH (Waldbronn, Germany), were carried out online during cyclic loading at 20 kHz. Fig. 2 shows the sinusoidal oscillation with the periodic time T in the first transversal bending eigenmode at different instants of time.

Figure 2: Oscillation of the CF-PPS specimen in the first transversal bending eigenmode at 20 kHz measured by 3D-SLV

This experiment has been carried out for displacement amplitudes in the nanometer scale to avoid any fatigue damage in the CFRP during the measurement. The experiment confirms the simulation results and visualizes the real sinusoidal oscillation of the CF-PPS specimen. To control the sinusoidal oscillation as well as to measure the displacement amplitudes, single spot laser vibrometry was used in every VHCF experiment. The analysis of the strain distribution at displacement amplitudes in the micrometer range reveals an expected maximum of shear strain in the area between the shoulders and the loading device. In the upper as well as lower outer fiber the highest tension and compression strains were measured. Based on the measured local strain values, the corresponding shear-, tension- and compression stresses could be calculated using Hooke's law for orthotropic materials and consequently the cyclic loads during the VHCF-experiments could be determined very precisely.

3 MATERIAL AND SPECIMEN DESIGN FOR VHCF EXPERIMENTS

The VHCF behavior of a commercially available carbon fiber fabric reinforced polyphenylene sulfide (CF-PPS) manufactured by Bond Laminates GmbH (Brilon, Germany) has been investigated. The polymer PPS is a semi-crystalline thermoplastic material with a glass transition temperature (T_g) of about 90°C and a melting temperature (T_{pm}) of around 290°C [7, 16]. In addition it offers a high stiffness, high chemical resistance and service temperatures of up to 200°C [7, 16] and is therefore increasingly used especially in the aircraft industry. The chosen laminate has an orthotropic layout and is built up of 19 layers of twill 2/2 C-fiber (HT) fabric with a mass per unit area of 200 g/m². The laminate thickness is 4 mm with a carbon fiber volume fraction of 54.8% and a density of 1.54 g/m³. The monotonic mechanical properties were determined in tensile and bending tests according to DIN EN ISO 527-4, DIN EN ISO 14129, DIN 65148 and DIN EN ISO 14125 and are summarized in Table 1.

	Young's Modulus in GPa	Ultimate Tensile Strength in MPa	Flexural Strength in MPa		Shear Strength in MPa
11-dir.	58 ± 2.0	659 ± 36	590 ± 10	13-dir.	37.7 ± 0.7
22-dir.	58 ± 1.6	585 ± 36	605 ± 17	23-dir.	35.4 ± 0.5

Table 1: Selected monotonic properties of CF-PPS

Additionally nine elastic constants have been determined in total to allow FEM simulations to adjust the frequency of the first bending eigenmode of the CFRP specimen to the resonance frequency of the ultrasonic resonance system at 20 kHz. The resulting specimen geometry with all dimensions is given in Fig. 3a. Fig. 3b shows a micrograph with the alternating stacking sequence of 0°- and 90°-C-fibers.

Figure 3: a) Specimen geometry for CF-PPS, b) Light optical micrograph of CF-PPS

Both edges on the long side of the specimens have been polished before the VHCF experiments to enable microscopic investigations to characterize and clarify fatigue damage mechanisms.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Constant amplitude tests

The fatigue behavior of the described CF-PPS up to 10^9 cycles (N_{limit}) has been investigated in cyclic 3-point bending tests at constant load amplitudes and a frequency of 20.27 kHz. All VHCF experiments have been realized with a monotonic mean load of $\tau_m = 12.3$ MPa. The cyclic shear stress amplitudes in 13-direction $\tau_{a,13}$ varied between 4.25 and 6.8 MPa. Consequently the load ratio of the experiments could be calculated between $R_\tau = 0.29$ and $R_\tau = 0.51$. The results are summarized in Fig. 4 where the cyclic shear stress amplitude $\tau_{a,13}$ is plotted versus the number of cycles to delamination N_{del} .

Figure 4: S- N_{del} -curve of CF-PPS in the VHCF regime

The log τ -log N -diagram shows clearly the exponential decrease of the bearable shear stress amplitude from 10^7 up to 10^9 cycles. All failed CF-PPS specimens showed a shear stress induced fatigue failure in the area between the shoulders and the loading device. Run outs have been achieved at lower shear stress amplitudes between 4.25 and 4.5 MPa without delaminations and are marked with green arrows. Nevertheless fatigue induced transversal cracks have been observed at these specimens. Four specimens reached the ultimate number of cycles of 10^9 at the shear stress amplitudes between 4.67 and 5.2 MPa showing significant fatigue damages in terms of so called meta-delaminations. They are marked with black arrows. However, these meta-delaminations did not cause an overcritical heating or a significant change in oscillation behavior during the ultrasonic fatigue tests. Additionally one specimen at a shear stress amplitude of $\tau_{a,13} = 4$ MPa has not been aborted after reaching the 10^9

cycles. However this specimen failed at nearly 2×10^9 cycles indicating the same failure mechanisms than all the other failed specimens. This leads to the assumption, that at least for the investigated CF-PPS and loading conditions, there seems to be no endurance limit. Nevertheless a fatigue strength of 4 MPa shear stress amplitude at 10^9 cycles was determined.

4.2 Microscopic investigations and VHCF failure analysis

Light optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) have been carried out to determine the current damage state and the proceeding fatigue damage for CF-PPS in the VHCF regime. Therefore the constant amplitude tests have been interrupted after approximately each 10 % of the estimated lifetime (number of cycles to delamination) or in case of an obvious fatigue damage. In Fig. 5 the accumulated fatigue damage with the corresponding fatigue damage levels for CF-PPS in the VHCF regime is summarized.

Figure 5: Damage sequence for CF-PPS in the VHCF regime

All further described fatigue damages occur in the areas of maximum shear stress of the CF-PPS specimen between the shoulder unit and the loading device.

By interrupting the VHCF-experiments for the first time fiber matrix debonding was observed. The crack initiation was localized at the fiber-matrix interface representing the weakest point of this composite (Fig. 5, blue framed micrograph) and propagates after re-loading to first transversal cracks. Their size was observed to one of the 90° rovings after roughly 40 % of the specimen's lifetime (Fig. 5, green framed micrograph). After about 60 % of the lifetime micro-delaminations between the 0° layer and the 90° layer were found (Fig. 5, yellow framed SEM micrograph). The micro-delaminations are characterized by a small crack opening less than 10 μm and a crack length clearly below 1 mm. A consolidation of transversal cracks and micro-delaminations was noted after further fatigue loading (Fig. 5, orange framed light optical micrograph). After about 70 % of the specimen's lifetime the existing cracks propagated up to meta-delaminations (Fig. 5, red framed micrograph). This means a crack opening clearly above 10 μm between the 0° layer and the 90° layer, crossing the complete 90° roving by an angle of roughly 45° and continuing along the next 0°/90° layer. The crack length at this stage is much longer than 1 mm. A similar damage evolution was also reported by Daggumati et al. and Lomov et al. [17, 18]. Until shortly before final failure a propagation and multiplication of meta-delaminations was observed. Finally a macro delamination evolved out of one or combining different meta-delaminations (Fig. 5, pink framed SEM micrograph) and stops the experiment due to a pronounced increase in temperature caused by internal friction of crack flanks. Also the oscillation behavior of the CF-PPS specimen changes due to the significant degradation of elastic properties followed by the loss of its first bending eigenmode at the testing frequency.

4.3 Evolution of surface crack density in the VHCF regime

During the interruptions of the constant amplitude tests the surface crack density of the CF-PPS specimens at different shear stress amplitudes has been determined using light optical microscopy for selected specimens. To that end all the cracks on the shear stress dominated areas (two at the front edge of the long side of the specimen and two at the rear side) have been counted and the crack length were measured, respectively. Each observed area has a size of 26.1 mm² corresponding to 8.15 mm in length and 3.20 mm in height. The surface crack density was calculated according to equation 1 and plotted for selected specimens over the normalized number of cycles to delamination in Fig. 6.

$$\text{Surface crack density} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{crack length } i}{\text{observed area}} \left[\frac{\mu\text{m}}{\mu\text{m}^2} \right] \quad (1)$$

The results show a similar behavior independent from the cyclic shear stress amplitude. At the beginning of the experiment an increase of the surface crack density were measured for all the specimens caused by fiber matrix debonding. From about 20 % up to 70 % no significant change in the surface crack density can be observed. After this plateau the surface crack density leaps to the end of the experiment caused by first and propagating meta-delaminations.

Figure 6: Evolution of surface crack density of CF-PPS in the VHCF regime at different shear stress amplitudes

Also the run out specimen ($N = N_{limit} = 1 \times 10^9$) at a shear stress amplitude of $\tau_{a,13} = 4.67$ MPa showed an increased course of the surface crack density over the loading cycles. Consequently significant fatigue damage was declared including several meta-delaminations even at this low shear load.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The fatigue behavior of carbon fiber fabric reinforced polyphenylene sulfide in the VHCF regime has been investigated using a new in house developed ultrasonic testing facility for cyclic 3-point bending at 20 kHz. By carrying out measurements with a 3D Scanning Laser vibrometer the validation of the simulated oscillation behavior of the fatigue specimens and the calibration of the fatigue loads could be realized. Furthermore an online monitoring procedure via IR-thermography and single spot Laser vibrometry was demonstrated. Caused by the geometrical layout of the experiment shear stress induced fatigue damage was established for all specimens. Constant amplitude tests showed an exponential decrease of the bearable shear stress amplitude from 10^7 up to 2×10^9 cycles. A fatigue limit of 4 MPa shear stress amplitude at 10^9 cycles was proved for the investigated CF-PPS. Via defined interruptions of the constant amplitude tests after approximately each 10 % of the estimated lifetime or in case of an obvious fatigue damage the failure mechanisms of CF-PPS in the VHCF regime could be documented and analyzed. The fatigue crack initiation could be localized on the fiber-matrix interface. Starting from the fiber-matrix debonding, first transversal cracks were documented. Micro- and meta-delaminations were observed after about 60 % and 70 % of the specimen's lifetime, respectively. The increasing number of the propagating meta-delaminations led to macro delaminations which cause the final failure due to significant decrease of stiffness. Additionally the surface crack density was determined in the interruptions of the constant amplitude tests showing a similar behavior for all investigated shear stress amplitudes. After an increase at the first 20 % of the specimen's lifetime and a distinct plateau up to 70 % of the lifetime, the surface crack density rises up to the final failure caused by macro delamination.

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